

**Towards a New Poetics:
A Discussion of Transformation
in English Language Literature.**

by Michael Yasui

Abstract: This essay is based on an excerpt from the forthcoming book, "Towards a New Poetic". The portion presented in this excerpt discusses how the oral tradition of poetry transformed from the 12th century to the 20th century. It does not deal with the misconception created in *Canonicist Studies* or the problem of gentrification in English Language Literature at its inception as a field of study. Rather it attempts to discuss how poetry, as a form of narration has developed with reference and in relation to the advent of the Novel.

The transition from the poetic narrative to the fictive narrative¹ was disrupted by the perversion of this antecedent's slip into Latin in the 17th and 18th centuries in order to allow access to a form of the English Language that had become lost for a time². It was only until the 19th century's attempt to categorize, quantify and catalog the English Language itself that Middle English began to re-immerge and assert and influence the Field of English Language Literature³ as something more than just household hearth-fire entertainment. As scholarly as this might sound, it must be noted that English Language Literature was still "traveling as baggage" so to speak. The first inquires into the Field begin with some genuine problems: what constituted material worth teaching—as frigid as the Victorian's were—it is hard to imagine them looking at Samuel Richardson's *Pamela* and not finding the story of a servant girl who endures the repeated attempts of her master to rape her as problematic content; or looking at Lawrence Stern's *Tristram Shandy* as a lighthearted attempt to convey the lofty meaning of life; even Mary Shelley's *Frankenstein*, the story of a grave robbing mad scientist who plays with dead bodies as ideal

for investigation into the higher meanings of life which remains the foundational principle for research in Classical Greek and Latin Literatures. Yes, that did not stop Hollywood from taking full advantage of these narrative to turn a profit. Nor the turn English Language Literature took with T.S. Eliot's affective stylistics and objective correlative, which are merely a restless twisting towards the rhetorical method⁴ that had become the chief pedagogical method before the 20th century. Nor does it account for the myriad of hypothesis which subsequently followed, all of which being sequestered by philosophical concerns exterior to the actual content of concern. The fact that each of these "schools of thought" are codified with the term "theory"—the blatant disregard for this word's actual meaning—demonstrate the fundamental flaw, none are in actual fact "theories." The true contention that arises from an unwillingness to recognize that they are, in fact, methods of "belief", and beliefs can never be anything more than mere hypothesis is a stigma that still plagues scholarly endeavors. What all of this demonstrates is that the study of English Language Literature has never been grounded in actual Science—a word itself with its own set of misconceptions—process or practice.

The English Language has had a scientific methodology applied to it in order to correctly define the words in the language. Yet, the Literature that the Language uses remains fraught with the absence of a recognition that a similitude in investigative methodology be applied. For the English Language alone, it was sufficient to derive definition from contextual usage that does not extend past that boundary. Yet, therein lies the problem: usage of the English Language alone, devoid of {time | place | author | presentation | reader | reception} will only yield an understanding of how the words, thus organized, work together to produce meaning as Eliot suggested with "organic unity of form". Looking at a quote from one of Flanner O'Conner's short stories, "A Good Man is Hard to Find," illuminates this problem, "...a dull young woman with a face 'as broad and innocent as a cabbage'". The word "with" suggests comparison and yields the operative metaphor comparing the qualities of this "face" to the qualities of the "cabbage": A cabbage is a flattened sphere and not at all egg-shaped like most heads, thus the face must also be abnormally shaped

producing the operative meaning that the woman is odd. The expression's metaphorical content can be analyzed but it cannot be extended to the author, the reader or further textual conditions. Looking at this quote in this way, it is clear that even Wimsatt and Beardsley's *Affective Fallacy*⁵ falls short in garnering meaning beyond the text. For English Language Literature to be Literature it must extend beyond the boundary of mere entertainment value. As humorous as it would be to take comparison based on shape, that very humor while possible in Mark Twain simply does not fit with O'Connor. The pursuant attenuation of narrative is incongruous to achieving a reading that Literature demands in a collectivized recognition in totality to surpass the primary purpose of entertainment—since that is truly the incubus of all art—making it something worthy as a field of scholarly pursuit. The criteria set forth in Aristotle's *Poetics* of value and merit being determined by the aesthetic quality of catharsis cannot be applied to English Language Literature.⁶

In examining the deviation from the poetic to the fictive, it becomes possible to understand the dislocating function of narrative today and the way in which the common cannon discerns Fiction from Literature. To exemplify this situation, it would be germane to remember that Shakespeare is revered not because his plays were original in content (narrative) but because the poetic control (form) exerted over the language to such dimension and at such depth in revealing that the narrative is so refined; the likes of it have yet to be produced by any other author or poet. It is the extended poetic construct and not the poetic narrative which yields reception as Literature today.

Narrative is created through both form and content. Although both form and content are subjects that occupy most discussions of Poetry, the concept of narrative seems to be largely ignored, or even disregarded as being something that can be guessed at, unless direct evidence that the poem was written with a narrative in mind. Dylan Thomas revealed that his famous villanelle (one of the most restrictive forms) that the poem contains content that is intended to express the feelings Thomas felt as he sat at his father's death bed. Yet, the poem does not evoke a sadness for the situation of the voice in the poem. Only the anger expressed

by that voice that, although cognizant of the fact that death is inevitable, affirms that death maybe stayed through sheer will. The over burdening power of the word, "rage" while the voice in the poem is directed at its audience, distracts from the fact that it is an expression of the voice in the poem's own frustration at its own futility. So distracting is this word, that the fact that the pain in watching someone die has been lost as a narrative. Yet, narrative is not just lost through the strength of language. Sassoon's "The Kiss" achieves this same end through the metaphor of divinity imparted to objects of destruction. The narrative of a soldier in World War I hunched over in the trenches praying to survive that bloody conflict is obliterated through the focus of that prayer. From post-Romantic poetry, a shift from narrative to form and content seems to have occurred in Poetry. The reasons for this shift are grounded in the study of English Language Literature as a bonified Field of Scholarship and a rejection of English Language Literature being merely a representation of the History of the English Language and its usage. After all, Literature for the masses must be approachable for the the masses. The Harry Potter series would not have sold as well as it did if on its cover had been a Rated-R sticker. After all, the series is about genocide with a narrative that begins with attempted infanticide, even the MPAA has standards. While the surprising thing about these standards are in that they are aimed more at the visual narrative rather than the textual narrative used to form the visual. This oddity is not confined to the silver screen. F. Scott Fitzgerald's tale of a hero who engages in serious criminal activities so that he may have an illicit affair with a married woman glosses over the enormity of this egregious behavior because he is a "romantic character". After all, as the narrator Nick Caraway admits in the opening page of the novel, "Gatsby turned out alright in the end"(Gatsby 3). When Nick makes this confession, he already knows that Gatsby has been murdered even if the reader does not. If Gatsby is dead; he paid for his sins with his life. It is the narrative that forces the reader to accept Nick's judgement despite the fact the hero of his tale is so radically immoral. Unlike this narrative in fiction, the narrative in poetry in the 20th century remains episodic at best. The closest alignment between poetry and fiction is James Joyce's *Ulysses* through its

"stream-of-conscious" style. Yet, Joyce like Eliot, in "The Wasteland" creates an allusion of antiquity through appropriated authority as an attempt to create through their narratives actual physical geographies that assume mythic proportions through the interactions of the characters as the narrative. Yet, the only really new thing in terms of the history of English Language Literature that was accomplished was the closeness to poetic form that Joyce's use of stream of consciousness achieved; while Eliot's poem merely repeats the Where's Waldo pattern of identify the allusion. Beyond that, both works are merely echoes of Dante's *Divine Comedy* with a mixture of the necessary episodic pantheon coopting the next and the next and the next stage in a progression of narratives. What remains clear, or at least should be clear, both fiction and poetry are fabricated entities. The process of classification that has been carried out by the numerous scholars is first based upon the precept that poetry is always Literature, but fiction, or prose is sometimes not.

The desolation created in the first 50 years of the 20th century by mankind's own hand—while not a new thing—produced a new reaction: a reaction that had been building through the 19th century and the advent of English Language Literature as a Field of Study into a unifying system of expression that cried out for classification. Eliot's recognition of that with the objective correlative, while recognizing the need for understanding artifice, failed to acknowledge the need for understanding how that artifice cannot be contained by its own boundaries because it failed to conclude that Literature must be all things created with language, but is in and of itself a created artifice. The need to assign value to each artifice in its relationship to man resulted in the acceptance of a splintered Universalism. To put it in simpler terms: the assumption that two oranges from the same tree will taste the same fails to acknowledge the subtle differences which will develop in relation to the variations in temperature, wind, sun, rain, ad nauseum that permeate the external situation of each orange until consumption, and yet, still, both are only oranges. This splintered universal makes possible an indifference to all the subtleties within the poetic narrative.

The complexity of poetic narrative can be observed from the ear-

liest of Old English poems to today. Here is an example of a late Middle English unsigned poem, c. 1450—bear in mind Middle English begins in 1066 A.D.—which begins with a third person narration concerned with a young clerk whose seduction of a young maiden and then in the final stanza through in medias res reveals that the narrator is, in fact, the young maiden. From a narrative perspective of form, the narrator announces the story, and then provides the story, and then only in the end flips the narration upside down to reveal that the narrator is the victim of the hero disrupting the narrative flow. The use of “the flip” in narrative strategy has always been very common. Most of F. Scott Fitzgerald’s writing makes use of it. Fitzgerald actually advises a young Ernest Hemingway to do the same in a letter. Although in that particular correspondence, the two-word reply is more famous. The more humorous aspect would have probably been lost on Hemingway—the expression used is an allusion to the aftermath of the Battle of Agincourt in 1415 directed at the losing French hubris. Likewise, the hubris of Joly Jankyn and Aleyson for their ill-advised liaison, and the revelation at the end of the lyric that the voice in the artifice is none other than the unfortunate maiden who is now with child. Be that as it may, it makes no difference to the meaning whether it was read, read aloud, or sung: It is a lyric poem as it meets all the criteria for being such. Likewise, anonymous, or not, it is an artifice because the poem was created with language to convey meaning through verbal compression and device—most notably to the narrative form is the device of enjambment. The elevation in the poem occurs through the ambiguity that creates the possibility of narrative shifts.

As observed in the first stanza, the poem begins with a poetic voice that speaks of Jankyn singing “with” a deviation/derivation of a proper noun in the third line. Yet, the proper noun is placed between single quote marks indicating that this word is imbued with some special meaning. Noticeable in the poem is that the correct form of capitalizing the first letter of a proper noun is observed, while the word in single quotations does not observe this rule. The lack of capitalization of the first letter suggests that the word is not a deviation/derivation of a name, and thence the voice is not describing Jankyn singing with another person but rather the way in

which Jankyn is singing. Given the fact that "aleyson" actually can mean either "first" or "with all one's heart" and the implication is that Jankyn is singing in a way which is exuberant beyond the normal attitude to say the least would seem accurate. Yet, the punctuation of the word adds a layer of ambiguity to the line as this adjective is seemingly morphed to a noun becomes a deviation/derivation of a woman's name. Hence, the punctuation implies that if the poem is received in an audible form or if it is read, the association created through the proximity of the preposition renders the reception to be a proper noun. Thus, either spoken or read the narrative form remains intact and implies that the voice of the poem is either a third person or the seduced victim now with child or that the voice in the poem is emphasizing the word as an exclamation through the use of the single quotation marks. Add to this layer the voicing, either through recitation or reading or unbridled mirth, the voice in the first stanza extends beyond the narrative content of the artifice reflecting Wimsatt and Beardsley's affective fallacy. The narrative shift in the second stanza from a third-person voice to a first-person voice with the usage of "I" in the first line of the second stanza only adds to the confusion of to whom the voice belongs.

As for the stanzas between the second and final, crude as the metaphorical content may be, only the repetition of the third line in stanza three, stanza four, and stanza five add to both the narrative form and the narrative content. The narrative form is easily understood though its mere repetition, but the narrative content contained in the repetition is somewhat dubious in meaning. This dubiousness serves both to inform and distract. This repeated line informs by paradoxically allowing for two contradictory receptions: One based on the coarse metaphor and one that derives from divinity produced in the final lines of each stanza. The narrative form from the third stanza to the final stanza operates by balancing the two preceding lines against the two successive lines. It is almost as if the anonymous source of the poem had fore-knowledge of tonal and atonal contrasts. The entire composition of the narrative content in the poem creates an entirety of straight-faced humor while preserving the reverence demanded by the lofty aspiration being celebrated in the poem which is

reinforced by the narrative form. This is, of course, Eliot's organic unity of form in action. Yet, a poem about a clerk who gets a young maiden pregnant seems to be a bit of stretch for the seriousness suggested by Eliot's own *topoi*. What seems to be missing from this artifice is the immortal element of time. Yet, "Yole" or "Yule" fulfills the requirement not only by reinforcing the Christian theme, but as a cultural theme. Thus, the artifice in action reflects the immortal memory of the eternal and by so doing implements the classical literary theme of immortality. However, even with the recognition that the artifice fulfills Aristotle's qualities of aesthetic merit while at the same time meeting Eliot's organic unity of form, and even though there was more than likely one such cleric whose behavior fits with that described in the poem implying a mimetic characteristic, both the narrative form and narrative content exist as organized phenomenon somewhat like an amoeba to be placed under the microscopic focus of the Literary Scholars in order to yield some type of discourse.

However, this discussion has been concerned at present with the transformative function of the artifice in its reliance on narrative form. Some 200 or so years after "Joly Jankyn's" appearance on scene that makes reliance on the use of narrative form; an example with a similar *topoi*—although perhaps a less graphic example—can be found through an examination of Andrew Marvell's "To His Coy Mistress." Since the title of the poem alone is enough to glean that while the presentation of the poem seems to rely on the narrative form, it is the narrative content which has become the chief concern. Although it should be noted that Shakespeare's Sonnets, published in 1609, artifice that pre-dates Marvell's poem, published 1681, are the most significant poems where the shift from narrative form to narrative content becomes visible, the problem of actual authorship surrounding the 154 Shakespearian contributions makes them extremely prohibitive for any worthwhile discussion regardless of how admirable these offerings may be. Marvell's poem, like Shakespeare's Sonnets was published posthumously, but the origin of authorship is not in question, and thus it is possible to associate the contribution of this artifice with Marvell in a way that is simply not possible with Shakespeare.

Marvell's poem is significantly different from "Jankyn" because

there is very little verbal compression created through usage of the narrative form in the latter. It is possible to even claim that the narrative form serves no other purpose other than to be merely decoration in the poem for its title; "To His Coy Mistress" creates a singular voice for the poem through the first two words "to his". This also creates the effect of making it seem like an epistolary, which is the same form that Samuel Richardson used in his novel *Pamela*. Thus, the voice in the poem is addressing a single listener | reader. Yet it is the paradox created from that description of this listener | reader that forces the language to supersede its own narrative form demanding greater attention to the narrative content. The adjective "coy" is only an affectation of "shyness" and is not a physical condition. Yet, the noun "mistress" is a word that screams for attention through its own illicit meaning. The voice in the poem is addressing a "secret love interest". While the unspoken "mistress" was something that Europe would not have scorned outright, in 17th century England it would have been downright unacceptable to make it so publicly visible. The word "mistress" surpasses the epistolary effect of the first two words through the implicit carnal desire inherent in both meaning and usage. Yet, what makes this poem even more unique is created in the poem when it moves past the mere imagery used to create the narrative content.

The first two lines of the poem are used to create a subjunctive condition, "Had we but world enough and time / this coyness, lady, were no crime". Usage of this grammatical device demonstrates the focus on narrative content rather than the devices of narrative form. The reduction of syntactic construction only seems to be necessary for creating the iambic tetrameter, and to create the ideal immediacy and intimacy for the narrative content. The imperfect couplet form only acts to support an ideal immediacy that today would be considered cliché. The stanzaic construction of the artifice of the three stanzas may appear to imply that narrative form is more relevant, but this is only because the narrative content contained within each stanza operate from a different perspective that forces comparisons in that narrative content. It is not until the second stanza that the artifice begins to assume a depth beyond the imagery offered in the first stanza.

Through the incitement of time at the beginning of the second stanza, Marvell's poem begins to appear to offer aspirations beyond the narrative content through the metaphorical reference to Greek mythology. Although, this line of poetry is extremely well-known, it should not be forgotten that the voice in the poem is merely making this appeal to time to obtain sexual gratification. What seems to have been lost on most is that this is one of the first instances of the usage of "carpe diem". A term, a theme, a philosophy that has influenced in one way or another most of the 20th century English Language Literature. And unlike "Jankyn", Marvell's poem is no longer about the past, but about the future, or at least a prospect of the future. The paradox of this change in narrative content is that it uses the past to make its argument about the future without any awareness of itself as it does so.

The two stories being told in these poems speak to the experience of being human. The truly interesting point is that it is the former poem and not the later poem that imparts any such revelation. The point is literally driven home in Jankyn's seventh stanza, line 32, "And on myn foot he trede". Whether or not this line is literal or metaphorical, the implication of the "accident" centers the listener | readers' attention of the narrative content by force of narrative form. Marvell's poem is merely an appeal, and nothing more as it is only reminiscent of the angst of being young. The narrative content of the poem fails to engage through the narrative form the more loft aspirations demanded in 20th century English Language Literature. Be that as it may, it does offer a glimpse of the transformation to come from focus on poetic narrative content to poetic narrative context; the final nail in the coffin so to speak.

The final shift that occurs between poetic narrative to fictive narrative that is truly significant is that which is heralded by Eliot's affective stylistics and objective correlative: it is a shift to poetic narrative context as the main function of artifice. The significance of this is that the shift almost occurs simultaneously with the coalescing of fictive narrative toward the end of the 19th century. One of the most recognizable examples is "To an Athlete Dying Young", published in the collection *A Shropshire Lad* by A. E. Housman in 1896; an elegy that relies both on poetic nar-

rative form and poetic narrative content, but it is through the poetic narrative context that it fulfills the demands of organic unity of form and achieves what the Romantic Poets sought to achieve—a discussion of the more-lofty issues of being human through the recognition of man's mortality. The concept of "Humanism" had not been present during the Romantic Period. It should also be noted that although similar artifice were being created by Walt Whitman and Emily Dickinson; these artifice fail to adhere as closely as Housman's artifice to poetic narrative form and poetic narrative content to be truly germane to this discussion, and while these two poets—as well as many others—touch upon the poetic narrative content and Humanism, they lack a completeness of both.

Housman's poem presents the sentiment of both immortality and mortality through its poetic narrative context through a truly imagined duality in the phenomenon of being. The notion of immortality is likened to the notion of being remembered rather than being immortal as in living forever. This may seem like a natural progression, but it implies that "death" is finite. The soul is no longer the immortal element purported by religious pundits. And although other poets attempt to reconcile "death"—like Emily Dickinson's "Because I could not Stop for Death"—the treatment places no finite limitation on the state. The narrative context in Dickinson's poem occurs postmortem which implies that the voice in the narrative of this poem contextualizing the situation in the notion of the immortality of the soul.

The truly remarkable thing about this phenomenological transition is the awareness of creating occurring between the end of the 19th century and the early 20th century is that it occurs simultaneously with the advent of what has become the conceptualization of English Language Literature still held today. Poetic narrative form is sublimated by fictive narrative form with the resultant categories in English Language Literature being identified as: Fiction, Poetry, and Drama. More remarkable still is the application of this to the two basic types of fiction: Fictive Literature (humanist) and Non-Fictive Literature (pulp). With the operative distinction that Fictive Literature is seeded with answers to the question of what it means to be human, while Non-Fictive Literature is merely entertain-

ment, the importance of each being the criteria for how well the work adheres to this aesthetic. All hypothesis introduced and explored in the 20th century stem from this inherently axiomatic distinction. The literary linguistic forms (dependency on verbal compression) of poetry and prose become poetry and fiction, with only the former retaining its status without the need to be further sublimated based upon consumption—what can be described as literary concern. Even as this momentum of English Language Literature, being originally a field of inquiry for the masses, attempted to overcome being pigeonholed as such through attaining that most dignified status of scholarly endeavor.

Appendix I

"Joly Jankin"
'Kyrie', so 'kyrie',
Jankin syngeth merie
With 'aleyson'.
As I went on Yole day
In our prosessyon
Knew I joly Jankin
Be his mery ton:
Kyrieleyson.
Jankin began the Offis
On the Yole day,
And yet me thynketh it dos me good,
So merie gan he say
'*Kyrieleyson*'.
Jankin red the Pistil
Ful fair and ful wel,
And yet me thinketh it dos me good,
As ever have I sel.
Kyrieleyson.

Jankin at the Sanctus
Craketh a merie note,
And yet me thinketh it dos me good –
I payed for his cote.
Kyrieleyson.

Jankin craketh notes
An hundred on a knot,
And yet he hakketh hem smaller
Than wortes to the pot.
Kyrieleyson.

Jankin at the Angnus
Bereth the pax-brede,
He twynkeled, but sayd nought,
And on myn foot he trede.

Kyrieleyson.

Benedicamus domino,
Crist fro schame me schilde.
Deo gracias therto –
Alas, I go with childe!
Kyrieleyson.

Endnotes

1 All language in any written form is a form of the vernacular. Hence, the concept of Vernacular verse is purely an application to create scholarly distinction which cannot in fact be applied to distinguish between recitation and reading.

2 See Jonathan Fruoco's *Chaucer's Polyphony: The Modern in Medieval Poetry*. Boston: De Gruyter (2020).

3 English Language Literature as an actual Scholarly Field begins in 1829 with the first actual degree program. This does not mean to imply that it begins in 1829, but only that it becomes recognized as an Academic pursuit and therefore must adhere to actual the rules and regulations of scholarship.

4 *Becoming T.S. Eliot: The Rhetoric of Voice and Audience in Inventions of "The March Hare"*. Jayme Stayer. p.3

5 The death of the authors' influence pointed out by William K. Wimsatt and Monroe Beardsley's theory operates through the recognition that the author and the intention executed through invention is not relevant as a structural unit to the created text, and therefore is unimportant in interpreting the text. The idea is similar to looking at a tree and wondering what God had intended when creating the tree.

6 The *en masse* response that occurred in Greek Drama is significantly transformed by the process of consumption of English Language Literature towards the end of the 19th century. The clear divisions in English Language Literature that formed, (fiction | poetry) (drama), implies that reception for the first group is no longer *en masse*, while the second group remains so.

Works Cites

- Alighieri, Dante. *La Divina Commedia*. Independent. (2021).
- Aristotle. *Poetics*. See Halliwell.
- Berry, Peter. *Beginning Theory: Introduction to Literary Theory and Culture*. Manchester Univ. Press. (2009).
- Davis, Robert con and Ronald Schleifer. *Contemporary Literary Criticism. Literary and Cultural Studies*. Longman. (1989).
- Dickenson, Emily. *The Complete Poems of Emily Dickenson*. Back Bay Books. (1997).
- Eliot, T.S. *The Sacred Wood*. Dover Publications. (2013).
- . *The Complete Poems and Plays*. Faber and Faber. (2004).
- Fitzgerald, F. Scott. *The Great Gatsby*. Scribner. (2018).
- Halliwell, Stephen. "Aristotle's Poetics" Bristol Classics: Bristol. (1989).
- Garbáty, Thomas. J. *Medieval English Literature*. D.C. Heath and Co. (1984).
- Goodby, John. *The Collected Poems of Dylan Thomas*. Weidenfeld & Nicolson. (2014).
- Houseman, A.E. *A Shropshire Lad*. Dover. (2016).
- "Joly Jankin" see Garbáty.
- Joyce, James. *Ulysses*. Vintage. (1986).
- Marvell, Andrew. "To His Coy Mistress." *The Complete Poetic Works of Andrew Marvell*. Delphi. (2014)
- O'conner, Flannery *A Good Man is Hard to Find, and Other Stories*. Mariner Books. (1977).
- "Poèmes et textes dits par Dylan Thomas." Hubretus Beirmenn. Antoine Girard. *Un Scelle D'Ecrivains*. (1991). Viewed on YouTube. <https://youtu.be/gWqG1q4DZOk>. Sept. 20, 2022.
- Richardson, Samuel. *Pamela: Or Virtue Rewarded*. Oxford World Classics. (2011).
- Rowling, J.K. *The Harry Potter Box Set*. Educa Books. (2018).
- Sassoon, Siegfried. "The Kiss." *The Penguin Book of First World War Poetry*. Penguin Classics. (2007).
- Shakespeare, William. *The Complete Works of Shakespeare*. Canterbury Classics. (2014).
- Shelley, Mary. *Frankenstein; Or, The Modern Prometheus*. Penguin. (2006).
- Sterne, Lawrence. *The Life and Opinions of Tristram Shandy: Gentleman*. Oxford World Classics. (2009).

- Thomas, Dylan. "Do not go gentle into that good night." *The Collected Poems of Dylan Thomas*. Weidenfeld & Nicolson. (2014).
- Turnbull, Andrew. *The Letters of F. Scott Fitzgerald*. Scribners. (1971).
- Whitman, Walt. *Leaves of Grass*. W W Norton & Co Inc. (2002).
- Wimsatt, W.K. and Monroe Beardsley. "The Intentional Fallacy." *Contemporary Literary Criticism. Literary and Cultural Studies*. Longman. (1989). (43-53).